

Rac-1aj

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xl-2-111-1-s-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	08281
Vial:	40	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xl 2 110 1 s rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/28/2021 9:59:25 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/28/2021 10:29:42 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.141	7985586	49.90	917612
2	10.738	8016575	50.10	593408

Asy-1aj

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xl-2-111-1-s-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	08281
Vial:	41	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xl 2 111 1 s
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/28/2021 10:15:07 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/28/2021 10:31:43 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.184	194141	1.97	22126
2	10.794	9663393	98.03	710636